

RESOLUTE
Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

Project number 777372

**WP1 – Generation of
 reagents and cell lines to
 allow system-wide study of
 the SLC family**

D1.5 SLC overexpression in HEK293

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V0.1	21 Jun 2021	First Draft (GW)
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V0.3	30 Jun 2021	Final draft for internal review (all Contributors)
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Publishable Summary

RESOLUTE aims to unlock the therapeutic potential of solute carriers (SLCs) in a systematic and coordinated effort. To reach this goal, loss- and gain-of-function studies using SLC knock-out (KO) and overexpression (OE) cell models are crucial. To create overexpression cell lines, we took advantage of the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line that allows site-directed integration of transgenes which results in uniform expression levels within a cell population without the need to subclone individual clones after target integration. To this date, we generated 446 cell pools, each expressing one of the known human SLCs with C-terminal hemagglutinin (HA) and Twin-Strep® tags. To improve expression levels and subcellular localization which might be affected by the tag position, we also generated 68 cell pools expressing SLCs with N-terminal HA and Twin-Strep® tags. For quality control and cell line characterization, we performed mycoplasma and sterility testing, Western Blotting, Immunofluorescence, and RNA-seq. As one of the work horses of the RESOLUTE consortium, these cell lines are widely used in applications such as assay development, interaction proteomics, ionomics and metabolomics. We anticipate that the data generated using these reagents as well as the cell lines themselves will have a highly significant and broad impact on SLC research.

Methods

Jump-In compatible expression vectors:

We previously generated expression vectors compatible with the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line with C-terminal HA and Twin-Strep® tags for 447 SLCs (see deliverable D1.1). Additionally, expression vectors with Nt-tagged SLC cDNAs (with STOP codons after the SLC ORF) were generated for a subset of targets for which expression levels and/or subcellular localization were believed to be affected by the tag position. All cDNAs had been optimized for human codon usage before gene synthesis.

Cell line generation:

Cell pools expressing individual SLC cDNAs were generated by transfecting the parental Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line with vectors encoding SLC cDNAs and Integrase according to the providers manual. After selection with Geneticin for at least ten days, surviving clones were pooled and further expanded to prepare freeze stocks and samples for cell line characterization. Transgene expression was induced by adding 1 µg/ml Doxycycline to the growth media (DMEM (Gibco 41965-039, sigma D5796) with 10% FBS (Gibco, Catalogue number: 10270, Lot number: 42F8381K) and 1% Pen/Strep (100 µg/ml).) for 24 hours. In total, we generated 446 Ct-tagged and 68 Nt-tagged Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression cell lines.

Quality control and multi-parameter cell line characterization:

a. Mycoplasma testing:

Samples were prepared according to the guidelines of the service provider (Eurofins) and were submitted for Mycoplasma testing by PCR. Furthermore, media was visually monitored for bacterial contaminations after culturing without antibiotics. We tested 463 out of the 514 (90%) of the generated HEK overexpression cell lines and did not identify any mycoplasma contaminations.

b. Western Blot:

Cells were lysed after 24 hours of transgene induction and probed for the presence of the tagged protein by Western Blotting using antibodies recognizing the HA epitope (#H6533, Sigma-Aldrich). The molecular weight of tagged SLCs was determined using a reference ladder and compared with the expected size based on the protein length. Cell lines expressing proteins of a size comparable to the expected size (+/- 20%) were labelled as “WB: Expressed” (309 cell lines). In case the observed band size differed more than 20% from the expected size, cell lines were labels as “WB: Uncertain” (48 cell lines). No clearly detectable band was observed for 26 cell lines (“WB: Not expressed”). For the remaining 89 Ct-tagged cell lines Western Blot assays will be completed shortly.

c. Subcellular localization by Immunofluorescence:

Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression pools were expanded from freeze stocks for a single passage and then seeded on laminin-coated high content imaging plates. After overnight cultivation, cells were treated with Doxycycline to induce transgene expression for 24h or were left untreated. Doxycycline was washed out and cells were left to grow for 24h. Antibodies or chemical probes were applied to stain 9 cellular compartments and the SLC-HA-Tag either prior or post fixation & permeabilization according to manufacturer's recommendations. Following several washing cycles, fluorophore labelled secondary anti species antibodies were incubated with the respective primary antibodies for 90min. Plates underwent a final wash, were sealed and images were recorded with 60x water immersion objectives on the Yokogawa CV7000 High Content Imager. Three z-slices across 3.75 μm thickness were taken to allow selection of the most appropriate image plane. 8 fields of 275x235 μm size and 4 well replicates resulting in about 2mm² total imaged area. All recorded original images were provided to the consortium to allow for post hoc image analysis. For initial analysis at Novartis, images were displayed using a proprietary viewer software (HCS-Tiles) linking image data to experiment-specific metadata and allowing for side-by-side comparisons of fluorescence patterns and hence detection of overlap between SLC-HA and any of the stained cellular compartments. In total, we generated high-quality subcellular localization data for 434 Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell lines.

Statements on co-localization were created following visual inspection by experts and are based on intensity distribution patterns as well as cell morphology. The relative intensity distribution of the HA-tag between cell compartments is provided as well as confidence ratings. In addition, an approximation to the absolute expression level of the SLC-HA per subcellular compartment based on 20x images is provided in a machine-readable format.

The following stains and antibodies were used: Nuclei - Hoechst 33342 (ThermoFisherScientific); Cytoplasm - HCS Cellmask Deep Red (ThermoFisherScientific); ER - anti kDEL (Enzolifesciences); Golgi - anti Giantin (Biolegend); Mitochondria - Mitotracker Orange CMTM Ros (ThermoFisherScientific); Lysosomes - anti Lamp2 (ThermoFisherScientific); Peroxisomes - anti PMP70 (Merck, Sigma); Endosomes - anti Rab9a (Abnova); Plasma Membrane - anti Na-K-ATPase (Abcam); SLCs - anti HA-Tag (ThermoFisherScientific).

All experimental details will be made available in the Experimental Protocol & Standard Operating Procedure: Expression analysis and Co-localization imaging of HEK293 TrexR4 wt SLC-OE cell pools by autumn 2021.

d. RNA-seq:

RNA was purified from doxycycline-induced and uninduced cells at CeMM and sent for library generation and deep sequencing on a NovaSeq machine at Boehringer Ingelheim. Expression of codon-optimized cDNAs was determined by mapping reads to all generated cDNA sequences to monitor transgene induction and cross-contamination with other cDNAs that may have occurred during plasmid preparation, cell transfection or cell line propagation. All cell lines with substantial amounts of contaminating transcripts (>5% of the cDNA that is primarily expressed) were re-generated using new plasmid preparations. We tolerated cell lines with <5% of contaminating transcripts since trace amounts of cross-contaminations may occur during RNA sample preparation in 96-well format and a small fraction of RNA-seq reads may be mapped to wrong cDNAs due to sequence similarity.

To this date, 342 Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpressing cell lines passed RNA-seq QC. RNA-seq samples for ~90% of the remaining cell lines have been prepared and are awaiting deep sequencing. To further characterize these cell lines, RNA-seq data of two uninduced and two induced replicates were used to quantify endogenous transcripts. Differential expression of genes was determined using DESeq2. This analysis revealed several transcriptional responses that could be clearly assigned to SLC function and allowed phenotypical clustering of several targets. We believe that these data represent a unique opportunity to systematically study the impact of the SLC transporter activity on the transcriptional profile of the cell.

Discussion

The generated HEK overexpressing cell lines proved to be of high value for the RESOLUTE consortium and are used for assay development, interaction proteomics, metabolomics, ionomics, transcriptomics, and binder generation and validation. With several hundred requests from our partners within the consortium as well as external collaborators, these cell lines are to date the most frequently used cell models within RESOLUTE. The main advantage of the overexpression cell line is the possibility to induce transgene expression in a tightly controlled manner. Using the uninduced cell line as control allows to detect even subtle changes without background noise such as clonal variations or batch effects when preparing samples from different cell lines.

The anticipated disadvantage of these cell lines is that overexpression of tagged proteins at levels that strongly exceed endogenous expression levels can affect localization, turnover, and function of the investigated target. Although we perform a rigorous quality control and characterization of these cells, these effects need to be considered when interpreting data generated using overexpression cell lines.

Conclusion

The aim to generate and characterize overexpression cell lines for >80% of the proposed 446 SLCs has been reached.

Repository for reagents and data

A reagent release proposal for all generated Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression cell lines will be submitted to all consortium partners by October 2021. After approval of the release, the modified cell lines can be distributed upon request and for research purpose only to non-RESOLUTE partners by CeMM or Novartis under Material Transfer Agreements following the reagent's General Terms and Conditions of Sale. CeMM and Novartis will distribute cell lines until June 2023 if the number of requests can be processed within the available resources.

A deposition of the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 overexpression cell lines at a cell bank is not possible since the General Terms and Conditions of Sale for the parental Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line does not allow a distribution of the original or modified cell lines against any kind of fee which would be required even for non-profit repositories. Moreover, these cell lines can be readily re-generated using the SLC cDNA plasmids that have been previously deposited by RESOLUTE at Addgene (<https://www.addgene.org/depositor-collections/resolute/>).

At this point, RESOLUTE partners cannot share modified Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell lines with non-consortium partners for commercial purposes according to the commercial licence of the cells. However, CeMM is currently investigating under which conditions these modified HEK293 Jump-in cell lines could be shared with third parties for commercial purposes. If this is possible, the recipient will have to negotiate a licence allowing commercial use with Thermo Fisher independently.

RNA-seq, Western Blotting and Immunofluorescence data will be made available to the public via the RESOLUTE web portal after the corresponding data release has been approved by the consortium partners. RNA-seq data will in addition be deposited at the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). The release for RNA-seq, Western Blot and IF localization data is planned for autumn 2021.

The RESOLUTE web portal will provide an overview on the HEK overexpression cell lines and allows to download sequencing results (raw data) for all experiments. Transcript and gene quantification (processed data) as well as the results of the differential expression analyses (analysed data) will be not only available for download in tabular format but can also be interactively explored via a dashboard visualization. Cell lines will be also linked to corresponding QC data, e.g. immunofluorescence data which are compiled in an Excel table and are available for download. In addition, representative images were compiled for each SLC in a high-resolution pdf document to provide members of the RESOLUTE consortium and the scientific community in general with a quick overview option. These documents are available for download for the corresponding cell line from the web portal.